

→ EH, NL, KP,
CP, GKA
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Adjacency structure of Set Solution

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The sparse part of the Set Solution normals, i.e. excluding the global (instrument) parameters, contains a non-zero element at position (i_1, i_2) if the two stars i_1 and i_2 are observed together in some superframe. The stars i_1 and i_2 are then adjacent. The adjacency structure is a list of all adjacent pairs and can be represented e.g. by the two arrays XADJ and ADJNCY as described by George and Liu, pp. 41ff.

In order to test and compare reordering algorithms it will be useful to simulate the adjacency structure for set solutions with various degree of dynamical smoothing (DS), i.e. with superframes of various length. (The shortest possible length equals the frame length 2.1333.. s; the longest useful superframe corresponds to the average time between jet actuations, about 500 s.) Since this structure can be simulated in a much simpler way than through a proper set simulation, I think it is worth while to write a special program for it. The following is a short description of such a program.

INPUT: (a) scanning law: $\alpha_{z0}, \delta_{z0}, \omega_0$ = initial attitude (at $t = 0$)
 v = speed of $\underline{z}$ -motion ($8.922 \cdot 10^{-7}$ r/s)
 w = spin velocity ($8.181 \cdot 10^{-4}$ r/s)
 θ = position angle of $\underline{z}$ -motion
 T = length of set (43200 s)

(b) star catalogue: rectangular equatorial coordinates u_i
(real or simulated)

(c) instrument: γ = basic angle (58°)
 ϕ = FOV size (0.9°)

(d) degree of DS: D = length of superframe

OUTPUT: adjacency structure N, XADJ, ADJNCY (N = number of stars)

METHOD:

The attitude motion is taken to be linear in the attitude angles:

$$\alpha_z = \alpha_{z0} + (v \sin \theta / \cos \delta_0) t, \quad \delta_z = \delta_{z0} + (v \cos \theta) t, \quad \omega = \omega_0 + \omega t \quad (1)$$

From this we may compute the $\underline{x}$ and $\underline{z}$ axes of the telescope; see (A.3.3):

$$\underline{z} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \delta_z \cos \alpha_z \\ \cos \delta_z \sin \alpha_z \\ \sin \delta_z \end{pmatrix} \quad \underline{x} = \begin{pmatrix} -\sin \alpha_z \cos \omega - \cos \alpha_z \sin \delta_z \sin \omega \\ \cos \alpha_z \cos \omega - \sin \alpha_z \sin \delta_z \sin \omega \\ \cos \delta_z \sin \omega \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

N.B.: Only 2 % of the sky is covered by the set. A condition for $\underline{u}_i$ to be inside the set area is:

$$\max(\underline{z}'_{0-i}, \underline{z}'_{T-i}) > -\sin \frac{\phi}{2} \quad \underline{\text{and}} \quad \min(\underline{z}'_{0-i}, \underline{z}'_{T-i}) < \sin \frac{\phi}{2} \quad (3)$$

where $\underline{z}_0$ and $\underline{z}_T$ are the positions of $\underline{z}$ at $t = 0$ and T (Lindgren, 1981-02-06).

The adjacency lists are successively built up by going through the superframes and finding out which set of stars $\{i_1, i_2, \dots\}$ is being observed in each superframe. All possible pairs from this set must be added to the adjacency lists. The procedure for finding these stars could be as follows.

Define

$$c_{\max} = \cos \frac{\gamma - \phi - \omega D}{2}, \quad c_{\min} = \cos \frac{\gamma + \phi + \omega D}{2}, \quad s = \sin \frac{\phi}{2} \quad (4)$$

For each superframe (j), compute midtime $t_j = (j - \frac{1}{2})D$ and hence $\underline{z}_j, \underline{x}_j$ from (1) - (2). Loop through the stars (i) and test the condition for inclusion in the superframe:

$$|\underline{z}'_{j-i}| < s \quad \underline{\text{and}} \quad c_{\min} < |\underline{x}'_{j-i}| < c_{\max} \quad (5)$$

If i is included in the superframe, augment the adjacency lists correspondingly. Next i . Next j .